
SIAMESE NETWORKS IN MEDICAL IMAGERY: CNN-BASED COMPARATIVE STUDY FOR BRAIN SYMMETRY SCORING

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ABSTRACT

Automated symmetry analysis in neonatal brain MRI remains a critical challenge for early detection of developmental abnormalities, yet existing deep learning approaches struggle with the unique characteristics of neonatal imaging. This paper presents a systematic evaluation of Siamese neural network architectures for this task, comparing five state-of-the-art backbone networks: ResNet, ResNeXt, MobileNet, VGG, and EfficientNet. We develop a novel training methodology utilizing controlled asymmetry simulation across 3,150 annotated axial brain views from a novel dataset. Our approach implements a progressive training protocol with asymmetries ranging from 1 mm² to 20 mm², enabling an evaluation of each architecture's detection capabilities. Comprehensive experiments demonstrate that VGG-based architectures achieve superior performance, with detection accuracy ranging from 76% for 7mm² asymmetries to 99% for asymmetries above 13.5 mm². Notably, our analysis reveals that models trained on medium-range asymmetries demonstrate better generalization capabilities across different scales. By providing a valuable resource for symmetry

analysis in neonatal neuroimaging and providing quantitative insights into architectural design choices for medical image deep learning, this work contributes to the development of more sensitive and robust diagnostic tools in neonatal diagnosis and care.

Keywords Symmetry analysis · Neonatal MRI dataset · Siamese networks · Medical image processing

1 Introduction

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is a method used to investigate the brain, which is capable of differentiating between white matter, cerebrospinal fluid, soft tissues, and grey matter [1], thus serving as an essential tool for diagnosing and treating brain-related conditions. As a diagnosis tool, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is essential in neonatal neuroimaging, helping to detect abnormal brain development, assess brain disorders, and monitor overall brain growth [2, 3]. It also provides a critical source of radiology data for advancing deep learning based computer vision techniques, particularly in anomaly detection [4] and image segmentation [5], with which methods can be developed and fine-tuned. However, neonatal cerebral magnetic resonance imaging presents different challenges compared to adult cerebral magnetic resonance imaging, mainly due to notable disparities in brain size and developmental characteristics [6]. The brains of newborns are significantly smaller, with volumes ranging from 100 to 600 ml, whereas the average volume of the adult brain is more than 1 liter [7]. In addition, neonatal brains exhibit a higher water content, less myelination, and less distinct cortical structures, all contributing to a reduced contrast between grey and white matter [8]. Physical variations between different ages of the brain are illustrated in Figure 1. From a computer vision point of view, this translates into different training or fine-tuning needs.

Furthermore, image acquisition is particularly challenging in clinical settings, where MRI scans of newborns are typically performed only when significant developmental concerns or complications arise. For healthy full-term infants, MRIs are considered unnecessary unless they are part of a research study, as the procedure is costly and stressful for the baby and the parents. Moreover, abnormal lesions disrupt the visual integrity of the brain, which results in structural alterations [9] and precipitates numerous adverse outcomes [10]. This is particularly evident in developmental disorders, as outlined in [11, 12].

Brain symmetry is a fundamental visual feature that is used in various studies to diagnose conditions such as developmental abnormalities and cognitive deficiencies [12]. This is supported by numerous studies on autism spectrum disorder [13], developmental language disorder [14], attention deficit and hyperactivity disorder [15], and dyslexia [16]. To describe brain structures in newborns and children in development, brain structural magnetic resonance imaging classification methods rely on scales and signals that qualitatively assess the symmetry of the brain hemispheres [17, 18]. These visual assessments are based on the manual identification of symmetrical regions by experts in axial brain images. The resulting scores are then combined to generate a final numerical evaluation metric that reflects the hemispheric symmetry of the brain. Given these clinical scales, comparative analysis of brain hemispheres and anatomical regions can significantly aid the diagnosis and treatment planning of neonate patients. However, the vast variability in anomalies and shapes, coupled with limited training data, makes automated analysis particularly challenging [19, 6, 1], and the complexity of brain asymmetry in neurodevelopmental disorders is highlighted by the fact that asymmetry patterns can vary across different regions and structures of the brain [20, 21].

Siamese networks [22] have been studied and applied in multiple contexts. In this work, the aim is to explore the limits of such architectures in the context of brain asymmetry assessment and to measure the minimum size of anomalies and asymmetries that can be detected by such algorithms.

In order to examine these inquiries comprehensively, we implemented and assessed siamese network architectures composed of diverse backbone structures. These were applied to

a new dataset, which is additionally introduced within this paper. Siamese networks are typically effective for image similarity tasks and comparisons [22], due to their efficient architecture made of a shared neural network backbone capable of processing pairs of images simultaneously, thereby detecting differences within a latent feature space.

This approach emphasizes the detection of symmetry and integrates insights from established scoring systems, which leverage certain cerebral regions within diverse algorithms. It aims to tackle the difficulties related to the unique size discrepancies and imaging attributes, such as contrast, that are typically observed in neonatal brain MRI scans. This method is closely aligned with clinical evaluation techniques, enhancing the relevance and interpretability of network results in medical contexts. Despite its critical importance, comprehensive neonatal brain MRI datasets remain scarce and are typically very small [6, 19]. This lack of training data restricts the development and evaluation of automated deep learning algorithms for newborns.

Figure 1: Comparative brain imaging over developmental age, reproduced from [23]. The gradual contrast change between neonatal and adult cerebral structures is due to the myelination of the white matter. The neonatal brain, markedly smaller in volume, presents unique interlaced shapes and color mapping compared to its adult counterpart.

The present work addresses the gaps discussed through three main contributions.

- A novel annotated dataset of neonatal brain magnetic resonance images, SymBrain, specifically designed for symmetry analysis and anomaly detection.
- A study of five multiple siamese network architectures built and tested with different backbones adapted for grayscale medical imaging, comparing various pre-trained neural network backbones and their respective sensibility to synthetically distorted halves.
- A demonstration of the ability of this approach to detect brain asymmetries of various sizes, demonstrating the potential of this approach to help radiologists diagnose, reduce interpretation time, and serve as a decision support system.

This paper is organised as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of related datasets and recent work in neonatal brain MRI analysis. Section 3 describes the new annotated SymBrain dataset, including its creation process and annotation methodology. Section 4 details our proposed Siamese network architectures and experimental setup. Section

5 details the training, validation, and testing process of each of the Siamese Networks implemented while assessing the prediction quality of the classification. Section 6 discusses the implications of our findings, the limitations of our approach, as well as potential future directions.

2 Datasets and Data Labeling Work

2.1 Neonatal Brain MRI Datasets

Due to the scarcity of clinical data and the restricted access to medical databases, the datasets for neonatal neuroimaging remain limited. These resources are essential to advance our understanding of early brain development and to improve the diagnosis of neurological conditions in newborns. Table 1 provides a summary of widely utilized open source datasets for neonatal brain magnetic resonance imaging.

Dataset Name	Sample Size	Year	Reference
ALBERTs Dataset	20*	2012	<i>Gousias et al.</i> [24]
NeoBrainS12 Dataset	20	2015	<i>Isgum et al.</i> [25]
Edinburgh Neonatal Atlas	33	2016	<i>Blesa et al.</i> [26]
(M-CRIB) Atlas	10	2017	<i>Alexander et al.</i> [27]
(dHCP) Second Release	558*	2018	<i>Hughes et al.</i> [28]

Table 1: Overview of comparable neonatal MRI datasets. * Number of individual volumetric scans, with both T1w and T2w images available.

The ALBERTs Dataset consists of 20 T1- and T2-weighted MRI scans of newborns, manually segmented into 50 anatomical regions [24]. NeoBrainS12 includes 20 preterm infant MRI scans acquired at different gestational ages. It was specifically designed to evaluate and compare the performance of various automatic neonatal brain segmentation algorithms [25]. The Edinburgh Neonatal Atlas comprises 33 term-equivalent neonatal MRI scans, with a detailed parcellation of the neonatal brain into 107 regions [26]. The Melbourne Children’s Regional Infant Brain (M-CRIB) Atlas is based on high-resolution T2w MRI scans of 10 term-born infants. It offers a detailed parcellation of the neonatal brain [27]. The Developing Human Connectome Project (dHCP) second release [28] includes 558 neonatal MRI scans, providing a wealth of structural and functional imaging data. It represents one of the largest open access resources for studying early brain development and is distinguished by its multi-modal nature, incorporating T1-weighted, T2-weighted, and functional MRI sequences. The images included in the second release used here were obtained from infants born and imaged between 24-44 weeks of age. The image volumes are provided with a radiology score that identifies anomalies. The dHCP dataset forms the basis of our current dataset and study and represents one of the most comprehensive and large-scale efforts in neonatal neuroimaging. This rich dataset enables a wide range of investigations into early brain development.

The datasets mentioned above facilitate the implementation of various computer vision tasks in neonatal neuroimaging. However, with the exception of the dHCP dataset, these resources are characterised by their sparsity and limited sample sizes. The heterogeneity in acquisition protocols further exacerbates data variability, consequently increasing the complexity of applying standard computer vision methodologies. In particular, a significant limitation across these datasets is the absence of explicit symmetrical hemisphere information, which could potentially enhance their utility for certain analytical approaches.

Although the dHCP dataset addresses the requisite image variety, it is constrained by limited annotations, particularly those related to symmetry detection. To address this gap, we propose a new two-dimensional annotation framework for the dHCP dataset. This resource not only augments the utility of an already valuable dataset, but also allows the evaluation of advancements in understanding of early brain development through the application of state-of-the-art deep learning methodologies. By providing these curated annotations, we

aim to facilitate accurate symmetry analyses, potentially leading to improved predictions of clinical outcomes for newborns.

2.2 Symmetry analysis and anomaly detection

The rapid brain development in newborns results in significant structural changes over short periods [6], making traditional adult brain imaging techniques less effective. This has encouraged the development of specialised computer vision algorithms for tasks such as brain segmentation [29], tissue segmentation [19], and structural parcellation [30]. The variability in image acquisition protocols across datasets requires robust pre-processing and harmonisation techniques [19]. Furthermore, the limited availability of large scale, annotated neonatal datasets has led to increased interest in transfer learning and few-shot learning approaches [31]. Recent advances in deep learning, particularly in convolutional neural networks and transformer architectures, have shown promising results in automating neonatal neuroimaging tasks leveraging the inherent symmetry of the brain and other parts of the body for anomaly detection in MRI [29, 32, 33]. Herzog et al. [34] proposed a deep learning-based approach that takes advantage of brain hemispheric symmetry to detect structural abnormalities. Their method uses a siamese network architecture, where it is used to compare corresponding regions across hemispheres, enabling the identification of subtle asymmetries that may indicate a pathology. In a similar vein, Wang et al. [35] developed a self-supervised learning framework that uses symmetry, improving the sensitivity of anomaly detection in cases with limited labelled data. Beyond the brain, siamese networks have been proposed in other sectors of the medical field, for example, for the detection of breast cancer [22, 36] and for the detection of diseases in the lungs [37, 38]. This work goes beyond a comparative study by also introducing Siamese networks with different backbones. Although previous studies demonstrate the potential of symmetry-based approaches in medical imaging, they do not offer a comparative analysis or extensive exploration of the limitations related to the performance of various symmetry-aware architectures on neonatal anatomical structures. The present work extends these contributions by specifically investigating the limitations and capabilities of siamese networks in the detection of one-sided anomalies with varying degrees of asymmetry. We introduce an evaluation framework that quantifies a Siamese network’s sensitivity to different sizes of structural asymmetries, ranging from subtle developmental variations to marked pathological changes. The method explicitly models the continuous spectrum of anatomical asymmetry observed in neonatal brain development. This framework allows to systematically assess the network’s performance across different severity levels of asymmetry, providing insights into both the strengths and limitations of siamese architectures in this context. Furthermore, while existing methods typically rely on pre-defined corresponding regions for comparison, our approach incorporates a general correspondence mechanism that identifies asymmetry depending on the model and the scale of noise its training was completed. These advances are particularly crucial for neonatal imaging, where rapid brain development can lead to significant variations in anatomical correspondence between subjects and age groups, especially in preterm infants.

3 Symbrain Dataset

To help with the analysis of anatomical symmetry of the newborn brain, we propose a new annotated dataset, stemming from the dHCP [28]. The project collected diffusion, structural, and functional MRI data, gathering rich datasets from hundreds of participants from different developmental age ranges. The research presented here and the annotations concern only structural MRI, available as MRI modalities weighed T1 (T1w) and T2-weighted (T2). The types of T1w and T2w images are essential MRI sequences used to capture and visualise various characteristics of brain tissue and its developmental processes [39]. T1w MRI accentuates the signal intensity of white matter in the brain, while attenuating the signal from water-rich structures, including cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) located between brain tissue and skull. In contrast, T2w magnetic resonance imaging enhances the signal from water-dominant tissues, making these regions more prominently visible. The original dHCP dataset comprises in its second release a combined set of 1050 fetal and neonatal T1w

and T2w volumetric scans, precisely 492 T1w and 558 T2w image volumes are accessed. These scans have been performed following a similar protocol in each case and have been collected from diverse populations, including healthy term-born infants, preterm infants, and fetuses with known congenital abnormalities. The scans were performed at multiple sites using state-of-the-art MRI machines and protocols specifically designed for neonatal and foetal imaging. All anatomical images for all dHCP subjects have had motion-corrected reconstruction [40]. The volume information from the original dataset can be visualised and extracted using different softwares, among which the Python package NiBabel [41] used in this study. Its API gives full access to header information (metadata) and image volume data as three-dimensional arrays. The raw image volume data from each of the T1w and T2w scans is retrieved as three-dimensional arrays. From the entire array of data, we select the depth of interest for visualisation of the so-called ‘slices’ in the coronal view, as these are the views typically used in clinical evaluations [18]. The volumes are of shape (290, 290, 203) pixels, with the third dimension being the z-axis, the coronal plane along which the cross-sectional slices are selected.

3.1 Slicing

To perform the slicing process on the three-dimensional dHCP volumes, three distinct depths along the vertical axis (also called frontal or coronal) are selected. A two-dimensional cross-section from the three-dimensional image volume is extracted for each depth level, resulting in three two-dimensional cross-sectional slices, per subject (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Representative visualization of the slices on the T1w and T2 volumes, at the three different depths selected on a volume of size (290, 290, 203). Corresponding depths on the z-axis are **D1**: 76px 1, **D2**: 101px 2, **D3**: 126px.

The three chosen depths on the coronal plane are the D1, D2, and D3 views along the vertical plane, as presented in Fig. 2. Since the volume shape is (290, 290, 203), the three selected depths represent the axial view at the 101, 76, and 126 z-axis depth (measured in pixels). Three two-dimensional sections were extracted from each of the 1050 volumes, resulting in a total of 3150 two-dimensional axial brain views used for further image analysis. Of the 3150 images, 1476 are T1w-type, and 1674 are T2w-type. Each slice provides a snapshot of the brain’s structure and can be analyzed separately to identify patterns and abnormalities.

The slices are then individually annotated. Since the annotation process for medical images can be complex and often time-consuming, the goal is to provide a clear and straightforward labeling process that helps computer vision models learn to identify and classify different features within the images. In the case of brain anomalies and the context of our research, measuring and identifying potential symmetrical patterns in medical MRI images is crucial for diagnosis and treatment planning.

3.2 Annotations

To annotate the images, the V7lab annotation software [42] was used to manually draw lines on the images to highlight areas of interest. In the v7lab, the Polyline tool is used to draw a straight line, composed of 2 points, on each slice. As illustrated in Figure 3, these annotations provide a visual representation of the separative hemispheric fissure. In addition, the estimation serves as a detailed reference for the separation of the hemispheres, which are then used as separate inputs of the symmetry detection model. Each two-dimensional slice is annotated with a single symmetry line. The coordinates of the start and end points of these line segments are saved as a set of two points, providing an approximation of the midline fissure when drawing the connecting line.

Figure 3: Data input preparation sample. From the midline annotation, the two separate hemispheres are obtained. The right hemispheres are rotated 180 degrees and mirrored. **A**: the raw slice obtained from the volume. **B**: annotated slice with the symmetry line. **C** and **D**: left and right hemispheres, extracted hemispheres, rotated and centered around the symmetry annotation.

3.3 Dataset access

The dataset and annotations are available online and can be freely downloaded from the repository [43]. Data processing methods are available to quickly get access to the dataset prepared for any downstream task. The dataset separates the two different modalities into two separate splits. The first split contains the 1476 T1w-type images, and the second split contains the 1674 T2w-type images. Detailed instructions for dataset usage are detailed in the dataset’s repository [44]. The dataset has the following attributes:

- **image**: PIL [45] formatted image representing the cross-section, of size 290x290 pixels.
- **line**: Straight line annotation coordinates in the image. Saved as $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2)$, representing the starting and end points of the line annotation, in the image coordinates.
- **radscore**: Volume radiology score based on potential visual artifacts detected in the entire volume from which the image was extracted, from [28].
- **session**: Session-ID of the original dHCP [28] dataset, used for scan identification retrieval. Three images are extracted from each volume-session.

4 Method

4.1 Setup and Data Preparation

We used the proposed SymBrain dataset to establish the foundational framework for developing a Siamese neural network capable of accurately analysing and comparing bilateral symmetry in neonatal brain MRI slices.

Specifically, the network training aims to develop the network’s ability to differentiate between dissimilar hemispheres. The network achieves accurate predictions by minimising the prediction distance, which quantifies the degree of difference between two input images in the network’s learnt feature space. Essentially, this means that the smaller the distance, the higher the predicted similarity between the input hemispheres. Once trained, the detection capacity of subtle asymmetries that indicate pathological changes in neonatal brains can be assessed, overcoming the challenges posed by unique variations in sizes and image characteristics present in neonatal brain MRI.

To prepare the dataset for training, several processing steps are necessary. Slices are aligned so that the line annotation is the centre of symmetry. Separate hemispheric halves are then obtained and centrally placed on each input image.

Then, to simulate visual artefacts and asymmetries in the anatomical view of the brain, a data augmentation strategy is implemented. This approach is necessary due to the limitations of the source dataset [28], which does not contain labels and does not include brain scans with pathological conditions. The image augmentation process is detailed below in Section 4.1.1.

The augmentation procedure was applied asymmetrically: simulated tumours were added to a randomly selected single hemisphere of selected image pairs. This approach creates pseudo-controlled examples of brain asymmetry, crucial for training and evaluating the Siamese network’s ability to detect and analyse such asymmetries.

Algorithm 1 Dataset with Noise Augmentation

```
BrainScans[], NoiseSize  $\in$  [0,9] Dataset of pairs with labels each BrainScan in  
BrainScans Left, Right  $\leftarrow$  BrainScan random(0,1) < 0.5 Dataset.add(Left, Right, label=0)  
Target  $\leftarrow$  randomLeft, Right position  $\leftarrow$  FindValidPosition(Target) AddNoise(Target,  
position, NoiseSize) Dataset.add(Left, Right, label=1) PartitionDataset(Dataset, [0.6, 0.2,  
0.2]) StratifiedFolds(Dataset)
```

Each pair, augmented or not, is labeled as for a binary classification task: 0 if no noise is added, and 1 if noise is present. The format of a sample in the prepared dataset is thus $(half1, half2, label)$, where $half1$ and $half2$ represent the two preprocessed hemispheres of the brain, label indicates the presence or absence of induced asymmetry.

4.1.1 Noise Augmentation Details

The image augmentation process was developed to simulate pathological conditions by introducing controlled asymmetries into the brain slices. Artificial lesions are implemented as round- or square-shaped gray areas of varying sizes, designed to simulate unilateral visual artifacts 5. To maintain anatomical plausibility, the position of each simulated lesion is restricted to fall entirely within the brain area, and the lesions are prevented from overlapping with the skull or extending beyond the brain border. In addition, placement is randomised within these constraints to prevent positional learning biases.

The dimensions of the simulated tumours were standardised, with consistent sizes for each level of augmentation. This standardisation enables systematic evaluation of the model’s classification ability relative to the size of the lesion. Ten different tumour sizes have been used, ranging from 2×2 to 40×40 pixels. These sizes correspond to approximately 1 to 20 mm^2 in physical dimensions, due to the resolution of the scanners used. The details of the dimensions are referenced in Table 2.

The resulting dataset comprises 3150 pairs of images, with an almost equal (variability due to the random selection of a pair for noise-augmentation or not) distribution of symmetrical

Table 2: Tumor size specifications used in noise augmentation. The in-plane resolution of the scanner is $0.8 \times 0.8 \text{ mm}^2$.

Size Level	Pixel Area (pixels ²)	Physical Area (mm ²)
1	2×2	1
2	6×6	3
3	10×10	5
4	14×14	7
5	18×18	9
6	23×23	11.5
7	27×27	13.5
8	31×31	15.5
9	35×35	17.5
10	40×40	20

and asymmetrical labelled samples. With this approach, the image pairs dataset makes a representative variety of brain depths, containing clearly defined normal (to the dataset limitation) and abnormal areas at various positions within the brain structure.

4.2 Models design: Learning Method and Siamese Networks

Building on the dataset of potential brain asymmetries described in the previous section, the study employs a Siamese network architecture to detect bilateral asymmetry in neonatal brain MRI slices.

In the context of this study, the network is designed to encode and compare pairs of patches from bilateral brain hemispheres. The fundamental principle underlying this approach is the classification of image pairs: unmodified hemisphere pairs are treated as belonging to the same class (considered here as symmetric), and pairs where one hemisphere has undergone noise augmentation are treated as belonging to different classes (or asymmetric).

Figure 4: Siamese network architecture with shared-weight subnetworks processing grayscale inputs. *When implemented, the noise augmentation is effective on only one half at a time to simulate unilateral asymmetry. After the Convolutional Backbone pass, concatenated outputs are passed through fully connected layers, yielding a final classification output. The CNN displayed stands for the various pre-trained backbones compared.

The classification framework aligns with the data augmentation strategy, where the objective is to train the model to maximise agreement between symmetric pairs and minimise agreement between asymmetric pairs.

To achieve this, the Siamese network computes and compares the reduced-dimension representations, or embeddings, of the input images in both similar and dissimilar scenarios. The dual-input structure of the Siamese network is ideally suited for this task, allowing for direct comparison of the representations of each hemisphere. In other words, and for any given pair of images, the network is designed to differentiate the inputs by comparing their representations and subsequently classify the pair as either similar (symmetric) or dissimilar (asymmetric). Figure 4 illustrates the Siamese network architecture employed with its dual input path. The subnetworks of the model, each a pre-trained model modified to accept 1-dimensional grayscale input, extract features from the images. By sharing weights, both subnetworks employ identical feature extraction methodologies for dual input, maintaining consistency in the analysis.

After the dual processing of inputs, the model’s architecture involves the concatenation of outputs from each subnetwork branch, which are subsequently passed through a few additional fully connected layers. These terminal layers perform comparative analysis of the extracted features, effectively quantifying the degree of similarity or dissimilarity between the hemispheric inputs. The final embeddings are used to output the probability that the two images are differentiated or not.

Consequently, the final output of the network is a single value that represents the similarity between the two input images. This architecture facilitates the integration and comparison of different pre-trained model backbones, allowing for performance evaluation across various configurations. The model’s design thus enables a comprehensive and consistent approach to analysing hemispheric asymmetry, leveraging the power of shared-weight architectures and pre-trained models to enhance feature extraction and comparison in medical image analysis.

The architectures of pre-trained convolution models employed within this study are ResNet [46], ResNext [47], MobileNet [48], VGG [49], EfficientNet [50], all with default layer weights obtained from training on general computer vision tasks [51]. Several modifications are implemented to adapt the pre-trained models to our downstream classification task. The convolutional network backbone is reconfigured to accommodate the grayscale domain, altering the first layer’s input dimensions from 3 (RGB) to 1 (grayscale). In addition, the terminal sequence of layers, typically responsible for classification in the original architectures, is removed. This modification results in each backbone outputting a lower-dimensional feature representation of the input data, effectively creating asymmetry-encoding embeddings. Thus, each modified model backbone processes one hemispheric half as input and generates a 1-dimensional tensor as output. The dimensionality of this output varies across the different backbones, ranging from 512 to 1024, due to the diverse architectures of the source models. The embeddings from both hemispheres are then concatenated into a single tensor, which serves as input for the final classifying Convolutional Neural Network. This terminal CNN completes the asymmetry detection process by producing the predicted label for the given pair of hemispheric images.

5 Results

5.1 Model Training

5.1.1 Experimental Setup, Training Process

To ensure robustness and performances, each network variant (differentiated by unique pre-trained backbones) was trained independently on the datasets. A k-fold cross-validation strategy (k=2) was used, combined with a holdout evaluation dataset. For each fold, 2266 image pairs were employed for training and 568 for validation during the training phase. The final test set, comprising 316 pairs (10% of the total dataset), remained unseen by the models throughout the training process.

Figure 5: Levels of random noise augmentation applied to the dataset during training on T1 and T2 modalities. **A**: maximum tumor size of 40x40 px. **B** and **C**: medium tumor size of 20x20 px, on both image modalities. **D**: minimum tumor size of 10x10 px. Each noise area had an equal random chance of being squared- or circle-shaped.

To facilitate fair comparison between models, key training hyperparameters were standardised with the following values : *Batch size*: 32 ; *Training epochs*: 10 ; *Optimizer*: Adadelta with an initial learning rate of 5e-3, combined with the StepLR learning rate scheduler.

Each model variant was trained on the 10 distinct noise categories (and datasets) as described in Section ??, resulting in a total of 50 trained models.

5.1.2 Evaluation

During the evaluation phase, the network sequentially processes pairs of images, producing a scalar output for each pair. This output is interpreted using a binary classification threshold of 0.5: values below this threshold are classified as matches, indicating images considered as similar, while values equal to or exceeding 0.5 are categorized as mismatches, suggesting dissimilar asymmetrical images. The model’s performance was quantified using standard classification metrics: accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and confusion matrices. These metrics provide a comprehensive assessment of each model’s discriminative capabilities in the symmetry detection task. As described in section ??, a 2-fold cross-validation strategy was used on the entire source dataset. Table 5.1.2 lists the best accuracy results of the different trained models against the different evaluation noise sizes.

[c]lllclclclclcl

Tumor size (mm ²)	Accuracy
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	Tumor size (mm ²)	Accuracy
1	0.50 0.50 0.50 0.50	0.50
3	0.50 0.51 0.50 0.50	0.52
5	0.50 0.50 0.50 0.50	0.55
7	0.56 0.50 0.50 0.50	0.76
9	0.66 0.53 0.50 0.50	0.81
11.5	0.81 0.55 0.50 0.50	0.89
13.5	0.85 0.58 0.51 0.52	0.99
15.5	0.92 0.57 0.52 0.61	0.99
17.5	0.98 0.58 0.54 0.77	0.99
20	0.99 0.59 0.59 0.98	0.99
	ResNet ResNeXt EffNet MobNet VGGNet	

The experimental results demonstrate significant variations in model performance across different tumor sizes, with clear patterns in detection capabilities. As shown in Table 5.1.2, all models initially struggle and exhibit baseline performance (accuracy ≈ 0.50) in distinguishing features at the lowest tumor sizes (1-5 mm²). This expected difficulty arises due to the limited planar resolution of the scanner (0.8 × 0.8 mm²), which itself is subject to measurement uncertainty. The model with the VGGNet and ResNet base emerge as the most efficient base architectures in this comparison, achieving remarkable accuracy of 0.99 for larger tumor sizes (from 15.5 mm² for VGGNet and 20 mm² for ResNet). VGGNet demonstrates particularly impressive early detection capabilities, showing meaningful improvement (0.76 accuracy) at just 7 mm², while ResNet requires larger tumor sizes (≥ 11.5 mm²) to achieve comparable performance of around 0.80 accuracy.

In contrast, ResNeXt, EfficientNet, and MobileNet show limited adaptation to increasing tumor sizes. ResNeXt and EfficientNet maintain near-baseline performance throughout the entire size range, and not exceeding 0.59 accuracy at the maximum 20 mm². MobileNet base presents an interesting case, remaining ineffective until 15.5 mm², after which it shows rapid and final improvement, achieving 0.98 accuracy at 20 mm².

These findings suggest that architectural complexity plays a crucial role in tumor detection across varying sizes. The threshold effect in the proper classification, and therefore feature detection, varies between the models but the VGGNet performances shows an important performance increase from 7 mm² (0.76 accuracy) and a reliable accuracy from 13.5 mm².

The evaluation is performed on unseen samples with different noise variations. This was completed with the VGGNet backbone model (the best performing model from the first training round), trained on all the different sizes of artificial noise.

5.1.3 Training with Smallest Tumours

When the best model was trained using small artificial tumours of size ranging from 1 to 5 mm², it did not demonstrate the ability to detect even the smallest tumors.

5.1.4 Training with Medium Tumours

When the best model was trained using medium artificial tumours (of size 5 to 9 mm²), the model demonstrated some increased detection performance and maintained its level of sensitivity in all larger tumour sizes. The model trained on a dataset with a noise size of 9.0 mm² was able to keep its relative accuracy of 0.7 on 11.5 mm² tumours to detect tumors up to 20.0 mm² during the evaluation phase 7. This suggests that training with middle-sized noise augmentations allowed the network to generalise well across a range of tumour sizes, enabling it to identify the smallest defined tumours and larger ones up to the maximal size evaluated here.

5.1.5 Training with Medium and Large Tumours

In the last set of experiments, the neural network was trained using larger artificial tumours. During evaluation, the model exhibited a noticeable decline in its ability to detect smaller tumours, especially the two trained on the largest tumour sizes of 17.5 and 20 mm², as highlighted in Table 8. Larger tumours were still reliably detected, down to 15.5 mm² (0.90 accuracy), but small tumors below 9 mm² were often missed and the accuracy result was reduced to 0.5 below 7 mm². This indicates that the model, having been exposed primarily to medium- to large-sized tumours during training, developed a bias towards detecting tumors of similar or larger sizes, thereby reducing its sensitivity to smaller abnormalities.

The results of the two experiments prove the general and intuitive relationship between the size of the noise augmentation used during training and the neural network's ability to detect tumors of varying sizes.

6 Discussion

The application of the Siamese network architectures to the SymBrain dataset represents a significant advancement in neonatal brain MRI analysis, in addressing the common chal-

Figure 6: Model performance over tumor size variations. Each model with the different CNN backbone was trained and evaluated on each fixed tumor size dataset. The network with the VGGNet backbone increased performance the fastest, closely followed by the ResNet backbone.

Figure 7: Representation of the best model performances depending on the training dataset, and noise size, variations. Three groups emerge: smallest tumor trained models (bottom two), medium (middle three) and largest (top five). Evaluation tumor sizes variations. The best performing model was trained on fixed size tumors and evaluated on unseen tumors of all sizes. Pattern: except for one, all models keep/increase their performances when evaluated on higher noise than in training. The results display the intuitive relationship between the size of the noise augmentation used during training and the neural network's ability to detect tumors of varying sizes. Three distinct groups of models emerge: those trained on the smallest tumors, medium-sized tumors, and the largest tumors.

allenges of limited training data and unbalanced classes in medical imaging. The creation of the slices dataset, involving the strategic addition of artificial noise to simulate asymmetries, was a crucial methodological decision. Although this approach was necessary to overcome the lack of annotated neonatal brain MRI data with pathological conditions, it simultaneously introduces limitations that warrant careful consideration. While the artificial nature of the induced asymmetries was necessary for training, it does not fully grasp the variability and complexity of real pathological conditions, potentially limiting the model's direct effectiveness in clinical applications. However, this methodology represents a vital step towards developing robust anomaly detection systems and exploring brain symmetry for diagnostic purposes. In the cases of larger tumours, the network's convergence and high-performance metrics underscore its efficacy in symmetry detection tasks, with certain pre-trained model backbones, notably the VGGNet architecture, demonstrating superior adaptability to this domain. The experiments examining tumour size variation yielded crucial insights into the model's generalisation capabilities, revealing its adeptness at detecting diverse tumor sizes when trained on small artificial tumours. To further validate these findings, we examined four specific cases that demonstrate the performance of the best models in different scenarios 9. The analysis included examples of small artificial noise (7 mm²) and larger noise (15.5 mm²) in both the T1w and T2w modalities, as well as real examples of adult MRI scans containing tumours from [52]. The VGGNet-based model consistently outperformed other architectures in all cases, particularly showing robust performance in detecting smaller asymmetries that proved challenging for other models. However, these promising results require cautious interpretation, as the synthetic nature of the asymmetries may potentially inflate and bias the performance metrics.

The results obtained highlight the critical role of training data composition in shaping model performance and sensitivity, while also proving the potential of symmetry-based approaches in identifying a spectrum of anomalies. Future research directions should prioritise the

Figure 8: Table of the VGG-backbone model evaluated on unseen tumor datasets under varying noise conditions. Each row corresponds to a specific tumor size used during training, while each column reflects the noise level applied during evaluation.

expansion of the training dataset to encompass a wider spectrum of authentic pathological conditions, potentially combining synthetic data with real clinical cases to bridge the gap between controlled experiments and practical applications. The current models’ reliance on simulated asymmetries remains to be evaluated on real-world clinical neonatal brain scans. The integration of additional imaging modalities and the implementation of longitudinal studies to track developmental trajectories could further enhance the clinical relevance of the model. In summary, the proposed Siamese network approach demonstrates considerable abilities in automated neonatal neuroimaging analysis; however, its clinical translation requires rigorous validation through prospective studies. The insights gained from this study not only advance our understanding of automated symmetry detection in neonatal brains but also lay a robust foundation for future innovations in this critical field of medical image analysis, paving the way for more sophisticated and clinically applicable anomaly detection systems.

7 Conclusion

This study introduces a novel annotated dataset of neonatal brain MRI images and demonstrates the effectiveness of a Siamese network architecture in analyzing bilateral symmetry. The proposed approach successfully addresses the challenges of limited data in medical imaging, particularly in the context of neonatal neuroimaging. The Siamese network, complemented with the integration of various pre-trained backbones, demonstrated significant capability in differentiating between symmetric and asymmetric brain halves, with the VGGNet-based architecture showing robust performance across all evaluations. The net-

Model Avg.	62%	56%	61%	59%
VGG model	95%	67%	85%	78%

Figure 9: Comparison of model performances on brain MRI cases with various noise levels and modalities. The images showcase four examples of specific cases datasets: (1) small noise, (2) larger noise, and (3-4) real examples from adult brain MRI in T1, T2 modalities with tumor. The performance is compared between the VGG-backbone model and the average of other models (Model Avg.). Across all cases, the VGG-backbone model demonstrates superior classification performance, as evidenced by higher accuracy percentages.

work’s sensitivity to different tumour sizes, with reliable detection from 9 mm^2 , provides important insights into the practical limitations and capabilities of such systems. These performance variations across different tumour sizes underscore the critical role of training data composition in developing robust symmetry detection systems. Although the results are promising, more research using more diverse and real-world pathological data is needed to validate our findings and ensure their applicability to neonatal MRI in clinical settings. The insights gained from this study lay the foundation for future advances in automated neonatal brain asymmetry detection, potentially contributing to improved early diagnosis and treatment planning in clinical settings. Future research should explore multi-scale approaches incorporating varying resolutions of imaging data, which could enhance anomaly detection across a wider range of sizes, pathologies, and imaging modalities. The symmetry analysis framework developed here can be extended to volumetric MRI, given appropriate annotations, by implementing 3D-equivalent versions of the models and siamese networks used in this study.

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